

Influence of Time, pH, Temperature, Organic Matter, Exchangeable Cation and Ionic Strength on the Adsorption of Benalate on Montmorillonites

O. P. BANSAL* and A. K. CHATURVEDI

Chemistry Department, D. S. College, Aligarh-202 001

Manuscript received 28 September 1989, revised 20 November 1992, accepted 7 January 1993

Adsorption of benalate has been examined in dilute aqueous suspensions of montmorillonite saturated with transition metal ions under variable conditions of time, pH, organic matter, temperature and solution ionic strength. Maximum adsorption of the pesticide occurred at pH 6.5. The adsorption isotherms were of S-type. The adsorption varied directly as the effective ionic radii of the exchangeable cation and inversely as the temperature, organic matter and ionic strength (upto 0.45), after which it became constant. The thermodynamic parameters indicated the process to be exothermic and the adsorption of pesticides on montmorillonite gave rise to an entropy loss. Various studies, viz. thermodynamic parameters and Freundlich adsorption isotherms revealed the existence of protonation and/or coordination between exchangeable cation of clay and oxygen of C=O group of benalate. However, desorption studies showed the presence of physical adsorption.

The present work reports the influence of time, pH, organic matter, temperature, solution ionic strength, and exchangeable cations on the nature of the adsorption, desorption of benalate from Cu-, Cd-, Zn- and Mn-montmorillonites.

Results and Discussion

The adsorption of benalate by Zn-, Cu-, Cd- and

Mn-saturated montmorillonites increased with time (Fig. 1) upto an asymptotic maximum after 36 h. This low rate of attaining equilibrium indicates that the process is only partly of chemical nature¹.

The effect of pH on adsorption of benalate on Zn-, Cu-, Cd- and Mn-montmorillonites (Fig. 2) showed that the adsorption increased upto the pH value of 6.5,

Fig. 1 Effect of time on the adsorption of benalate by (●)Cd, (○)Mn, (▲)Cu and (△)Zn montmorillonites

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on the adsorption of benalate by (●)Cd, (○)Mn, (▲)Cu and (△)Zn montmorillonites.

and thereafter decreased. The pK value of benalate in distilled water, determined by the conductivity method, was 6.4. Its potentiometric titrations with 0.001 M HCl or 0.001 M NaOH showed that benalate behaves as an ampholyte with pK_a 4.2 and pK_b 8.1. As expected, maximum adsorption occurs at a pH value near pK value. At pH value < 6.5 H^+ -benalate and > 6.5 Na^+ -benalate may be formed by interaction with H^+ from (0.1 M HCl) and Na^+ -from (0.1 M NaOH) ions. These ion-complexes are not adsorbed by the clay. In the absence of competition from H^+ or Na^+ ions at a pH 6.5, a direct association of pesticide with the cations on the clay surface probably occurs giving maximum adsorption.

The adsorption data followed the Freundlich equation,

$$\log X/m = \log K + 1/n (\log C)$$

where X/m is the amount of pesticide adsorbed ($\mu g g^{-1}$) by clay, C the equilibrium concentration in solution ($\mu g ml^{-1}$) and K (sorption capacity) and $1/n$ (sorption intensity) are Freundlich constants under the specified conditions; K ($ml g^{-1} clay$) is the quantity adsorbed for a unit equilibrium concentration ($C = 1 \mu g ml^{-1}$). The values of Freundlich constant ($1/n$) which reflects the degree of non-linearity of

adsorption during benalate adsorption on Zn-, Cu-, Cd- and Mn-montmorillonites were more than unity indicating a S-type of isotherm (Fig. 3 as representative) as defined by Giles *et al.*². It indicates that new sites become available to the solute as the adsorption occurs, and there is competition of solvent for sites on the adsorbing surface. Such types of results have also been reported by Moreale and Van Bladel³ and Bansal⁴.

Fig. 3. Adsorption of benalate on Cd montmorillonite at (●) 18, (▲) 33 and (○) $48 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

The adsorption of benalate followed the order : Cd- > Mn- > Cu- > Zn-montmorillonite, which is in accordance with effective ionic radii of exchangeable cations. These inferences are also supported by the values of Freundlich constants K and $1/n$. A rise in temperature from 18 ± 0.5 to $48 \pm 0.5^\circ$ results in a decrease of adsorption of benalate which is also supported by the corresponding values of the Freundlich constants (Table 1). The decrease in adsorption may be due to decrease in physical adsorption⁵, caused by weakening of van der Waals forces of attraction between pesticide and clay surface.

The adsorption of benalate on Zn-, Cu-, Cd- and Mn-montmorillonites decreased progressively as more humic acid was added (Fig. 4 as representative). It may be due to preferential adsorption of organic

TABLE 1—FREUNDLICH ADSORPTION PARAMETERS OF BENALATE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES ON MONIMORILLONITE SATURATED WITH DIFFERENT

Cation (II)	$K \pm S^*$			$1/n \pm S$		
	18°	33°	48°	18°	33°	48°
Cd	15.85 (0.18)	14.89 (0.17)	14.03 (0.18)	1.250 (0.003)	1.213 (0.005)	1.175 (0.005)
Mn	15.14 (0.20)	14.26 (0.19)	13.40 (0.20)	1.200 (0.004)	1.165 (0.003)	1.145 (0.005)
Cu	14.59 (0.20)	13.84 (0.19)	13.06 (0.16)	1.175 (0.003)	1.145 (0.005)	1.125 (0.004)
Zn	14.03 (0.19)	13.40 (0.16)	12.68 (0.14)	1.150 (0.007)	1.120 (0.005)	1.105 (0.006)

*S Values are those of the standard error.

matter on clay surface linked through exchangeable cations on the clay and ionized carboxyl group in humic acid (clay-M-OOCR)⁶.

Fig. 4 Adsorption of benalate on Cd-montmorillonite with (●), (○), (△), (▲) 0, 25, 50 and 100 mg of humic acid

Adsorption experiments for benalate were carried out at the ionic strength range 0.18–1.8. The results showed (Table 2) that adsorption of pesticide decreased as ionic strength increased upto 0.45, and then it became constant. The adsorption was more affected where Cd, Mn and Cu were the saturating cation rather than Zn. The decrease in adsorption with increasing ionic strength (0.0 to 0.45) was from 23 to 28.4%, which may be due to (i) decrease in activity of pesticide in solution as the ionic strength increases⁷, (ii) formation of non-adsorbable metal-pesticide complex in solution⁸ and (iii) competition of pesticide with

increasing amount of cations for the adsorption sites⁹.

The results of desorption (Table 3) indicated that part of benalate adsorbed on Zn-, Cu-, Cd- and Mn-montmorillonite can be desorbed by water or solutions of inorganic salts. The desorption of pesticide was more by salt solution than by distilled water which may

TABLE 2—ADSORPTION OF BENALATE ON MONIMORILLONITE SATURATED WITH DIFFERENT TRANSITIONAL METAL IONS AT SEVERAL IONIC STRENGTHS (OF APPROPRIATE SALT) AT 33 ± 0.5°

Ionic strength (I)	Cation (II)	Amount of adsorbed benalate mmol / 100 g clay
0.000	Cd	83.0
	Mn	81.0
	Cu	79.2
	Zn	76.0
0.018	Cd	78.0
	Mn	75.8
	Cu	74.0
	Zn	71.4
0.045	Cd	72.4
	Mn	70.4
	Cu	69.0
	Zn	66.0
0.09	Cd	58.4
	Mn	66.6
	Cu	65.2
	Zn	63.4
0.18	Cd	64.0
	Mn	62.0
	Cu	61.0
	Zn	59.4
0.36	Cd	61.6
	Mn	60.0
	Cu	58.8
	Zn	57.4
0.45	Cd	60.4
	Mn	58.6
0.9	Cu	57.4
	Zn	56.2

be due to (i) a flocculation effect, resulting from polymer bridges between the mineral particles in suspensions and (ii) coagulation effect on dispersed solids due to a decrease in the electrical double layer at the interface solution of dispersed particle¹⁰. Results of desorption indicated that appreciable adsorption of benalate on crystal basal surface of clay occurred by ionic interactions and by long-range attractive forces.

10) SD of $\ln C_s/C_e$ ^{13,11}. The ΔG^0 , ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 were calculated using usual expressions. The errors in ΔG^0 , ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 were calculated from the errors in K_0 and ΔH^0 using error propagation techniques¹². The data of thermodynamic parameters are reported in Table 4.

The values of K_0 (Table 4) was found to be more than unity which is indicative of the fact that benalate

TABLE 3—DESORPTION OF BENALATE FROM PESTICIDE-CLAY COMPLEXES (mmol/100 g) BY WATER, 0.02 M KCl AND 0.01 M CaCl₂ AT 33 ± 0.5⁰

Saturating cation (II)	Amount of pesticide adsorbed	Amount of pesticide desorbed by water	Amount of pesticide desorbed by KCl	Amount of pesticide desorbed by CaCl ₂
	mmol / 100 g	mmol / 100 g	mmol / 100 g	mmol / 100 g
Cd	83.0	17.2	33.6	33.6
Mn	81.0	16.2	32.8	33.0
Cu	79.0	16.4	32.0	32.2
Zn	76.0	16.0	33.0	32.6

The thermodynamic equilibrium constant (K_0) was calculated with the help of Biggar and Cheung¹¹ model. In order to accurately estimate K_0 , the same values of C_s at all the three temperatures were used due to slight non-linearity in relationship between $\ln(C_s/C_e)$ and C_s . Here C_s is μg of solute adsorbed per ml of solvent in contact with the adsorbent surface and C_e is μg of solute per ml of solvent in the equilibrium solution. Five mean values of $\log X/m$ for each of different cation-saturated montmorillonites were used to calculate five values of C_s and C_e for each replication at each temperature. Values of C_e were determined from the appropriate regression of $\log C_e$ vs $\log X/m$. The error in K_0 was estimated from $\text{SD} = (C_s/C_e) (\ln$

has a high preference for montmorillonite surface. The K_0 values decreased in the order : Cd- > Mn- > Cu- > Zn-montmorillonite, confirming our earlier findings on order of adsorption.

The values of ΔG^0 are negative, having the magnitude from -12.37 to -11.63 kJ mol^{-1} , and increased with the rise in temperature. The negative values of ΔG^0 pointed towards the spontaneity of the reaction with a greater affinity of montmorillonite for benalate. The ΔG^0 values also support our earlier conclusions concerning the affinity of pesticide on the Zn-, Cu-, Cd- and Mn-montmorillonite. The values of enthalpy change (ΔH^0) (Table 4) for benalate adsorption on transition metal-saturated montmorillonite, indicated

TABLE 4—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR BENALATE ADSORPTION ON MONTMORILLONITE SATURATED WITH TRANSITIONAL METAL IONS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE CALCULATED ACCORDING TO BIGGAR AND CHEUNG *

Cation (II)	K_0			ΔG^0 kJ mol^{-1}			ΔH^0 kJ mol^{-1}	ΔS^0 $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$
	18 ⁰	33 ⁰	48 ⁰	18 ⁰	33 ⁰	48 ⁰		
Cd	166 ± 4.1	119.0 ± 2.6	89.1 ± 2.0	-12.37 (± 0.04)	-12.16 (± 0.04)	-11.98 (± 0.03)	-16.22 ± 0.05	-13.24 ± 0.06
Mn	155 ± 3.0	114.0 ± 2.5	85.5 ± 1.6	-12.25 (± 0.03)	-12.03 (± 0.03)	-11.87 (± 0.05)	-15.72 ± 0.04	-12.02 ± 0.07
Cu	150 ± 3.6	108.5 ± 2.4	82.0 ± 1.7	-12.12 (± 0.05)	-11.94 (± 0.04)	-11.76 (± 0.03)	-15.05 ± 0.12	-10.17 ± 0.12
Zn	142 ± 3.0	104.0 ± 2.3	78.0 ± 1.1	-11.99 (± 0.06)	-11.82 (± 0.04)	-11.63 (± 0.02)	-14.62 ± 0.11	-9.17 ± 0.13

* Values are means ± S.D., Ref. 11.

the exothermic nature of the reaction, and the adsorption is energetically favoured. The ΔH^0 values also show that adsorption occurred through bonding mechanism¹³. The negative values of entropy change (ΔS^0) indicated that adsorption complexes of the pesticide formed are stable. Association, fixation or immobilisation of pesticide molecule as a result of adsorption resulted in the loss of the degree of freedom of the pesticide molecule producing negative entropy effects.

The above results indicate that benalate,

may be adsorbed by coordination between exchangeable transition metal cations and oxygen of amide group directly (I) or through water molecules (II)¹⁴ and/or by protonation¹⁵, hydrogen bonding and dipole association or van der Waals forces as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Experimental

The <2 μm fraction of montmorillonite (bentonite sample from Akli in Rajasthan, India) was purified by sedimentation and centrifugation and converted into chloride-free Na-saturated clay by treating it with 1 N NaCl¹⁶. Homoionic suspensions of Cu-, Cd-, Zn- and Mn-montmorillonites were obtained from Na-form by ion-exchange technique³. The pH values of the Cu-, Cd-, Zn- and Mn-saturated montmorillonite suspensions recorded were 5.9, 6.0, 6.0 and 5.8 respectively. The concentrations of the suspensions were in the range 13.1–15.9 g dm^{-3} . The cation-exchange capacity (CEC) of the Na-montmorillonite was 72 m.e./100 g clay¹⁷. The total surface area, determined by the reported method¹⁸ was found to be 668, 660, 646 and 638 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$ for the Cu-, Cd-, Zn- and Mn-montmorillonites respectively.

The effect of time on adsorption was studied by taking the appropriate clay suspension (10 ml) in several glass-stoppered tubes and treating with 15 ml of benalate solution (7000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in $\text{H}_2\text{O} : \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ (1 : 1)). The samples were continuously shaken for various intervals of time (from 2 to 72 h), then

centrifuged and benalate estimated spectrophotometrically at 420 nm¹⁹. The amount of the pesticide adsorbed was obtained from the amount added minus that remaining in the supernatants.

The effect of the equilibrium pH on adsorption was investigated at eight different pH values, ranging from 2 to 12, and were obtained by adding 0.1 N HCl or 0.1 M NaOH as required. The appropriate clay suspension (10 ml) and benalate (15 ml) (concentration as above) were shaken in glass-stoppered tubes for 40 h, then centrifuged and benalate adsorbed was calculated as above. To study the effect of temperature adsorption was measured similarly with variable amount (0–15 ml) of benalate at 18, 33 and 48 ± 0.5°.

To determine the influence of solution ionic strength, the pesticide solution (15 ml; having concentrations as above) which was initially prepared in 0.01, 0.025, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.25, 0.5 and 1 M of Cd(NO₃)₂, Cu(NO₃)₂, Zn(NO₃)₂ and Mn(NO₃)₂ solution were equilibrated with the appropriate clay suspension (10 ml) at 33 ± 0.5°. The amount of benalate was calculated as above.

The adsorption in the presence of organic matter was investigated in another set of experiments at 18 ± 0.5° by adding 25, 50 or 100 mg of humic acid to each of the montmorillonite suspension used for adsorption.

In the desorption experiments, the appropriate clay suspensions (10 ml) were shaken with benalate (15 ml) (concentration as above) for 40 h and then centrifuged. The supernatant solution was withdrawn and an aliquot taken for determination of benalate. The amount of benalate adsorbed was calculated from the decrease in concentration in solution. The benalate-retaining clay sample was then treated with water, 5 ml of 0.02 M KCl or 5 ml of 0.01 M CaCl₂ respectively, the volume then adjusted to 25 ml with distilled water,

and the samples were shaken for 40 h and centrifuged as above. The supernatant (15 ml) was then withdrawn and benalate-retaining clay sample was treated again with 15 ml of water, KCl or CaCl₂, then shaken for 40 h, centrifuged and benalate in both the supernatant solutions was estimated as above.

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